

STUDY ON THE PROCESS OF CONTINUOUSLY PRODUCED THERMOPLASTIC HONEYCOMB

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SUMMARY: A new concept of continuously manufactured thermoplastic honeycomb, ThermHex, is expected to be applied in broad areas, due to its cost-effective production and processing techniques. This paper will focus on the evaluation of the processability for one thermoplastic material, PP, so as to predict the material behaviour in real process conditions and finally optimize the process to acquire qualified products. The thermoforming step is investigated by using visco-elastic material model to analyze the polymer mechanical response under thermoforming conditions. The fusion bonding step is studied by the numerical analysis on heating transfer and polymer flow behaviour.

KEYWORDS: honeycomb, thermoforming, fusion bonding, material behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich materials, especially with honeycomb cores, have outstanding mechanical performance and are lighter than conventional structural materials. They have been widely used in the aerospace industry during the last decades. However, the use of sandwich materials is very limited in civil applications due to the high cost and labour intensive production of honeycomb cores. A continuous process of thermoplastic honeycomb core, ThermHex, has been patented and is under development at K.U. Leuven. The ThermHex process starts from one continuous thermoplastic sheet. After a series of processing steps, thermoforming of half-hexagonal cells, folding of half-hexagonal cells to honeycomb geometry, internal welding (fusion bonding), the horizontal half-hexagonal rows become the vertical cell walls of the honeycomb structure. The sandwich panel can also be produced continuously afterwards when two skins are laminated directly onto the produced honeycomb. Fig. 1 shows the schematic view of the continuous ThermHex core and panel production. The detailed information can be found in references [1] and [2].

Fig. 1: Continuous thermoplastic honeycomb and panel production concept

In this paper, only the thermoforming and welding steps are investigated in detail since material morphology changes during both processing steps. For the web-folding step, the material folds at elastic range and no obvious physical and chemical changes happen inside the polymer; therefore it will not be discussed here.

THERMOFORMING STUDY

Problem Statement

The ThermHex process starts with a Thermoforming process. A contact preheating tool and a subsequent forming unit, which can be deep drawing tools or rotational vacuum forming tools, thermoform the flat sheet into a half-hexagonal web precisely. Fig. 2 shows the pictures of a lab-scale deep drawing unit and a rotational vacuum forming unit.

Fig. 2: The lab-scale deep drawing unit (left) and rotational vacuum forming unit (right)

The accuracy of the geometries of the formed half-hexagonal web has large influence on later processing steps and the resulting honeycomb mechanical properties. In order to successfully fulfil the forming step, thermoplastic materials should meet two requirements: (1) They can be evenly stretched up to a large strain without any material tearing, cracking and splitting, after being heated up to the right processing temperature. (2) The material should be still transportable after the preheating, before the deep drawing or vacuum forming.

From above two points, it is obvious that the preheating temperature is very critical to ensure the forming quality. Inadequate heating may cause bad forming quality, such as local thinning, tearing and cracking by deep drawing unit, or insufficient stretching by vacuum forming unit. Over heating may cause ‘semi-fluid’ material which leads to significant material distortion and generate large difficulties for transferring the sheet material from the contact preheating tools to the forming tools. Moreover, due to the memory effect of thermoplastic material’s thermo-mechanical history, which is also called as anelastic strain recovery (ASR) effect [3], the thermoformed half-hexagonal web tends to ‘form back’ to the flat sheet while it is heated up again during the later welding process step. This effect hence deteriorates the hexagonal geometries of the cells and might degrade the mechanical performance of the core or of the sandwich panels, see Fig. 3. By analyzing the material visco-elastic behaviour and the thermo-mechanical history, the ASR effect can be dramatically reduced.

Fig. 3: The produced honeycomb cores with and without ASR effect.

Material

The honeycomb is made from Polypropylene sheet with 4% Talc filler. The original sheet thickness is 0.2 mm. The Young’s modulus is 1.7 GPa and the yield stress is 21 MPa, which

are determined by a standard tensile test. Since the talc filler's content is rather little in the material, pure Polypropylene thermal properties are simply taken in this study.

Polymer Test and Discussion

Standard polymer tests on the material are conducted first before the lab-scale thermoforming test to obtain the general profile of the material. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) are the basic test methods to acquire polymer's thermal mechanical characters which are useful to help determine the thermoforming temperature. Fig. 4 shows the results of DMA and DSC tests. The temperature scanning of DMA was done with tension mode at frequency of 1 Hz and ramp of 5 °C/min. The DSC test also has the same temperature ramp of 5 °C/min.

The results from DMA and DSC tests indicate that the material undergoes phase change at about 167 °C which is the melting point of PP. The storage modulus of material drops dramatically at melting point. The possible thermoforming temperature should be above melting point to have good material stretch ability. Since the material should be transportable after heating, the thermoforming temperature must not be too high. Meanwhile the thermoforming time should be determined carefully to prevent the ASR occurring later, thereafter the detailed material thermo-mechanical behaviour should be checked with certain material model.

Fig. 4: DSC and DMA results of the talc-PP material.

Visco-elastic Model and Material Characterization

The PP material undergoing the ThermHex process steps can be described basically by the use of stress-time, strain-time, and temperature-time curves demonstrated in Fig. 5. The forming and welding temperature are represented as T_f and T_w in Fig. 5. Apparently T_f and T_w are not constant during the process varying with the change of time. The first step in the ThermHex process is the thermoforming of the thermoplastic sheet material. After being heated up to the right temperature, driven by the vacuum or the deep drawing tools, the PP is stretched and formed to the half hexagonal web. This leads to a gradually increasing strain in the material. The stress in the material is assumed to be constant as creep phenomenon. Although this assumption is not completely true, the system still should be simplified to conduct the analysis. The stretching of the material stops when the material fully touches the female mould. After that, the vacuum or the deep drawing tools continues to keep the pressure on the material for certain time before the end of forming step. The internal stress of the material actually is relaxing (decreasing) while the strain still stays at its maximum. Meanwhile, the temperature is cooling down. At the end of forming, the vacuum or the deep drawing tools are released and the material internal stress drops to zero whereas the strain keeps the maximum. Thereafter the formed material is to be folded and welded. During the welding, the material temperature goes up again and there is no stress applied on the material,

however the strain will recover for the sake of anelasticity of the thermoplastic material. The residual strain after welding is the permanent strain in the final honeycomb product which is expected to be same as the maximum strain. The residual is actually the material viscous strain. If the material is not relaxed adequately during the forming, the recovery strain of the welding could impair the final geometry of the honeycomb.

Herein one linear visco-elastic material model is applied to describe the material behaviour during the ThermHex process steps. The general 1-D constitutive equation of an isotropic visco-elastic material can be written as a hereditary integral form according to Boltzmann Superposition Principle as the following [4]:

$$\sigma(t) = \varepsilon_0 E(t) + \int_0^t E(t-\tau) \left(\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} \right)_{t=\tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

Where $\sigma(t)$ is the stress, $E(t)$ is the relaxation modulus, ε is the strain, ε_0 is the initial instantaneous strain, t is the time, τ is the moment when the strain rate changes. Obviously in Eqn. 2, the bulk effect is neglected due to the assumption of the incompressible material. The generalized relaxation modulus can be written in Eqn. 2 [4]:

$$E(t) = E_\infty + \sum_{i=1}^N E_i \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_i}\right) \quad (2)$$

E_∞ , E_i , are elastic moduli. τ_i is relaxation time, . However, to acquire the material's strain response, the constitutive equation can be written in another form by using of the material creep compliance [3]:

$$\varepsilon(t) = \sigma_0 J(t) + \int_0^t J(t-\tau) \left(\frac{d\sigma}{dt} \right)_{t=\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

Where $J(t)$ is the creep compliance. The relationship between $E(t)$ and $J(t)$ follows [4]:

$$\bar{J}(s)\bar{E}(s) = \frac{1}{s^2} \quad (4)$$

Where $\bar{J}(s)$ and $\bar{E}(s)$ are the Laplace transforms of the creep compliance $J(t)$ ($L[J(t)] \rightarrow \bar{J}(s)$) and the relaxation modulus $E(t)$ ($L[E(t)] \rightarrow \bar{E}(s)$), s is the transform variable.

Fig. 5: Schematic view of material stress, strain, temperature history for ThermHex process. Time is not continuous between forming and welding steps, where stress keeps zero, strain and temperature keep constant values.

Since the thermoplastic material's relaxation modulus and creep compliance are time, temperature dependant, and the ThermHex process is not an isothermal procedure, the temperature effect on the material should be considered. According to the thermorheological simplicity, the visco-elastic response to the time translates with change in temperature, in relaxation times $\tau(t)$, it is described as [3]:

$$\tau(T) = \frac{\tau(T_r)}{A(T, T_r)} \quad (5)$$

T_r is the reference temperature, $A(T, T_r)$ is the WLF shift function [3]:

$$\log A(T, T_r) = -\frac{C_1(T - T_r)}{C_2 + T - T_r} \quad (6)$$

C_1, C_2 are constants. The PP material relaxation modulus were measured and characterized by rotational rheometer at 180 °C and DMA machine at 150 °C. Because 167 °C is the transition (melting) point of the PP material and the material's morphology changes dramatically at this point, therefore two reference points are needed to obtain the shift functions above and below the transition point. The discrete data are fitted by using of a second order exponential decay curve which is actually same as Eqn. 2 with $N=2$. Fig. 6 shows the results of the curve fitting. The R-squared values of both fitting curves are almost 1, which shows very good fitting results. The relaxation modulus at 150 °C and 180 °C are then:

$$E(t) = 27.04 + 4.14 \exp(-t/14.04) + 6.08 \exp(-t/96.39) \quad (T=150 \text{ °C}) \quad (7)$$

$$E(t) = 0.003 + 0.10 \exp(-t/0.03) + 0.026 \exp(-t/0.167) \quad (T=180 \text{ °C}) \quad (8)$$

Fig. 6: The relaxation modulus data and their fitting curves at 150 °C and 180 °C.

With the aforementioned equations and the provided the processing parameters, thus the material strain response through the ThermHex process can be numerically solved. Moreover, the full scale material forming simulation can be done with any commercial FEA software to acquire the proper processing parameters without trial-and-error test.

Thermoforming Optimisation

Herein we only give some initial result of 1-D material strain response under the provided simplified processing parameters. The presumed process parameters are described as follows: the material first isothermally creeps at 180 °C for 0.5 second, and then relaxes for 0.5 second at 180 °C and 150 °C. The transient cooling effect of the contacting mould is neglected to only reveal the importance of the relaxation temperature with such simplified calculation. The relaxation basically is not an isothermal procedure. After that, the material cools down rapidly and the relaxation at lower temperatures is neglected for the sake of very long relaxation time. Finally the material endures another isothermal heating (at the welding step) at 150 °C and 180 °C and the strain recovers without any external stress applied. The calculated stress and strain responses are shown below in Fig. 7 and compared.

(a) Creep at 180 °C → Relaxation at 180 °C → Recovery at 150 °C

(b) Creep at 180 °C → Relaxation at 150 °C → Recovery at 180 °C

Fig. 7: The numerical results of 1-D stress and strain responses for the visco-elastic material undergoing thermoforming, relaxing and recovering.

One can see from the results above that the relaxation stage plays an important role on the final residual strain. When the relaxation temperature is raised up from 150 °C to 180 °C, the ASR effect diminishes dramatically. It is indicated that the material should be heated up as much as possible and the forming tools must be also at high temperature to prevent fast cooling of the formed material to ensure a good relaxation.

FUSION BONDING STUDY

Problem Statement

The fusion bonding step is implemented by a double-belt laminator, which consists of heating sections, two counter calibration rollers, cooling section, and two rotational PTFE belts pressed against each other, see Fig. 8b. The folded honeycomb held by the moving belts is first fed into the laminator and heated up, then the calibration rollers apply certain pressure on the heated honeycomb to achieve the cell wall-skin strip bonding. At last, the cooling section cools down the bonded honeycomb. Several features should be stressed out as follows:

- 1) A certain out-of-plane pressure should be kept upon the folded honeycomb to prohibit the folded structure springing back during the heating. Fortunately, the heating tools can provide about 0.05MPa to 0.1 MPa pressure.
- 2) The cell wall top and bottom parts should be sufficiently heated, whereas the cell wall internal part is demanded not to be overheated to have sufficient resistance against the pressure. The pressure should be well controlled to prevent any cell wall collapsing.
- 3) The cooling section should have sufficient cooling efficiency to provide rapid cooling.

Fig. 8: (a) Three bonding circumstances of the folded honeycomb fusion bonding step. The cell wall-skin strip bonding is expected to achieve. (b) Double-belt laminator and its heating and cooling scheme.

Heat Transfer model

The investigation of fusion bonding starts from the heat transfer analysis. A 1-D transient heat transfer model, which is based on the homogenized honeycomb, and a FE model, which is based on the detailed hexagonal honeycomb geometry, are built up to investigate the heat

transfer behaviour of the fusion bonding. Three types of boundary conditions are applied as follows [5]:

1). Dirichlet condition: The value of the temperature is given at fixed value.

$$T = T_{heat} \quad (\text{at } z = d_h/2 + d_b + d_e/2 \text{ and } t = 0 \rightarrow t = t_{heat}) \quad (9)$$

$$T = T_{cool} \quad (\text{at } z = d_h/2 + d_b + d_e/2 \text{ and } t = t_{heat} \rightarrow t = t_{cool}) \quad (10)$$

2). Robbins condition: The heat flux at the solid-solid contact interface is determined by the difference between the temperatures at the surfaces of contacting solids.

$$k_{(e)}(T) \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=(d_h/2+d_b)+} = h_{(eb)} \cdot (T_e - T_b) = k_{(b)}(T) \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=(d_h/2+d_b)-} = h_{(eb)} \cdot (T_b - T_e) \quad (11)$$

$$k_{(b)}(T) \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=(d_h/2)-} = h_{(bh)} \cdot (T_b - T_h) = k_{(h)}(T) \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=(d_h/2)+} = h_{(bh)} \cdot (T_h - T_b) \quad (12)$$

Where k is the heat conductivity of the material, and h is the contact conductance between the contacting pair. T is the temperatures at the contacting interface.

3). Neumann condition: The temperature gradient is given as a constant. Here in the model the constant is zero.

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=0} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The applied positions of three conditions are show in Fig. 9:

Fig. 9: Different boundary conditions and their applied positions

The FE transient analysis of the unit cell temperature field during the heating/cooling is implemented by using of ANSYS® software. The heating/cooling tool, PTFE belt, skin strip, hexagonal unit cell are modeled separately using 3D thermal solid element (SOLID 70), see Fig. 10. By assuming the symmetric condition, a half unit cell and a heating/cooling tool with full height are modeled, together with two layers of skin strip and belt in between. The interfacial contact conductances between different materials are implemented in the model by using a contact element pair (CONTA173 and TARGE170). The trapped air in the cell is modeled as solid material contacting cell walls and skin strips.

Fig. 10: Finite element model of unit cell. From the top to the bottom, heating/cooling tool, PTFE belt, skin strip, hexagonal cell walls, and trapped air are modelled.

The result of temperature-time spectrum along the thickness of the honeycomb from the 1-D model is shown in Fig. 11a. The temperature distribution inside the unit cell at a certain moment from the FEA model is show in Fig. 11b. Moreover, the results of temperature measurement at three positions are compared to the models in Fig. 12. It shows a very good agreement between the experimental value and the numerical results. With both two models, one is capable to predict temperature distribution and evolution for any process settings, to

ensure the melting of polymer at the top of the honeycomb and the good pressure resistance at the center of the honeycomb.

Fig. 11: The results of temperature distribution from 1-D model (a) and FE model (b).

Fig. 12: The comparison between the models and the experimental results.

Polymer Flow model

Based on the thermoplastic intimate contact model from Lee [6], further adaption is applied for the honeycomb fusion bonding case. The verticle cell wall is divided into a undeformable solid part and another deformable molten part. The solid part stands above the molten part. Once the bonding pressure is applied onto the honeycomb, the molten part of cell walls start to deform. Fig. 13 shows the change of cross section of one single cell wall during the bonding. After a certain time, the rectangular size of cell wall molten part will transform from $a_0 \times b_0$ to $a \times b$. b_0 is a constant representing the thickness of single cell wall t_c . a_0 , a , b are dependent on how much cell wall deforms or the honeycomb thickness decrease after bonding. They are variables in the model.

Based on the assumptions of volume and mass conservation, laminar flow of the molten polymer and with certain boundary conditions, the mathematical expression of the deformation for a single molten cell wall is developed and the final equation is described as follows:

$$f = -\mu a_0^3 b_0^3 \left(\frac{1}{5a_0^5} - \frac{1}{5a^5} \right) / t \Big|_{a=a_0}^{a=a} \quad (14)$$

Where f is the pressure applied on the cell wall, t is the time needed when a_0 deforms to a , μ is the material viscosity. Eqn. 14 can be adapted to the honeycomb geometry to acquire the full scale honeycomb bonding pressure, which is show in the following equation:

$$\sigma_{bond} = 1.33 \frac{f}{\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} L} = 1.54 \frac{f}{L} \quad (15)$$

Where L is the line segment length of the hexagonal cell inside honeycomb.

Fig. 13: The deformation of the cell wall molten part, where fusion bonding occurs (left). The mass conservation of an infinitesimal volume is shown for the molten polymer flow. (right).

Welding Optimisation

Several examples of calculated bonding processing parameters based on Eqn. 14 and Eqn. 15 are shown in Fig. 14 to Fig. 15. The PP viscosity is measured from 0.001 to 0.01 MPa*sec at the temperature range from 165 °C to 200 °C. The geometry of the molten polymer a_0 , b_0 and the cell size L are adopted as 0.5 mm, 0.16 mm, 3.7 mm. a_0 is determined by the process, which requires the maximum decrease of the honeycomb height is less than 1 mm. For each side of cell wall, the original deformable a_0 must be 0.5 mm then. In fact a_0 should be defined from where the temperature is above the melting point in the cell wall. However, it is still assumed here only 0.5 mm cell wall at the top and bottom sides reach the melting point.

Fig. 14: The theoretical correlations of the required honeycomb bonding pressure vs. time (left) and the bonding pressure vs. the deformation level a (right). Different viscosities are also compared. The value of $a = 0.2$ mm after deformation. The corresponding honeycomb height decrease is then 0.6 mm (left). The time of bonding is set as $t = 0.1$ sec (right)

From the results in Fig. 14 (left), it can be seen easily that the theoretically required deformation time (bonding time) is quite short (less than 0.1 sec). The pressing time by the couter rollers, which is about 0.2 sec, sufficiently satisfies the required bonding time when the viscosity is fairly low. However, if an extreme fast production speed and hence a very short bonding time, e.g. 0.01 second, is demanded, the required bonding pressure can then rise up singularly. Thus the machine might not be able to provide such high pressure, which would result in less deformation of cell wall molten area and smaller inadequate intimate contact finally. Meanwhile the viscosity also influences the bonding pressure significantly. A higher viscosity leads to a higher bonding pressure linearly. Thus the cell wall bonding area is required to be heated up adequately to reduce the viscosity for the bonding. Certainly excessive over-heating must be prevented especially for the cell wall center areas. The results of Fig. 14 (right) indicate that under certain condition ($t = 0.1$ sec), the cell wall molten area can not be compressed dramatically thin, e.g. a is compressed less than 0.1 mm, if so the needed pressure will increase singularly and exceed the machine's limit. In fact, when the compression force is very high and the polymer viscosity is very low, the melt situation will become much complex and the current theory based on laminar flow will not be valid anymore. Nevertheless it still gives useful predictions when the processing conditions are not too extreme. Fig. 15 gives an overview of correlations between multiple processing

parameters. As can be seen, when the required time is decreased and the cell wall is much compressed, the required bonding pressure will increase dramatically. This graph can be used for process optimisation to determine the proper processing window. For example, with the given production speed, machine limits, and desired core height, the required material viscosity (function of temperature) can be deduced from the Fig. 15. Afterwards with the help of two heat transfer models and material properties, the heating and cooling parameters can be determined finally, which are the fusion bonding settings for the laminator. Or with the given machine temperature, pressure, speed settings, and the deduced material viscosity, the needed bonding time can be determined for the honeycombs with different final heights. Then compare this bonding time to the machine's running speed to verify the initial settings. If necessary, further loops must be done until the optimisation is achieved.

Fig. 15: The theoretical correlations of required honeycomb bonding pressure vs. deformation level and time. The different viscosities corresponding to four surfaces from below to above in the graph are 0.001 MPa·sec, 0.004 MPa·sec, 0.007 MPa·sec, 0.01 MPa·sec. The machine provided pressure range is marked between two flat planes of 0.1 MPa and 0.05 MPa in the graph.

CONCLUSION

The new concept of the continuously produced thermoplastic honeycomb ThermHex is investigated here and the optimal processing parameters of different processing steps can be determined for a certain polymer by the methodology presented in this paper.

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